

TERMS OF CLOTHING AND JEWELRY IN THE WORKS OF QAZI MAULIK

Orinbaeva Jupargul

Karakalpak State University Named After Berdakh

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Annotation: The article discusses the linguistic features of Qazi Maulik's works. Terms of clothing and jewelry in the poet's works analyzed with examples.

Key words: linguistics, Old Turkic language, clothing and jewelry terms, linguistic analysis, ethnocultural features, ethnography, ethnographisms.

Clothing names are used productively in everyday life. From the earliest stages of human development, clothing forms began to appear. Representatives of each nation, regardless of their spoken language, traditions, as well as the great influence of civilization, are distinguished from other peoples by the peculiarity of their dress.

The Karakalpak people have a rich national heritage. They are reflected in the customs and traditions of our people, in their everyday life, as well as in their clothing. From this perspective, the distinctive national characteristics of the people, their development from early times into one of the Turkic peoples with their own distinct place, are well preserved in their traditions and clothing. A deep study of such national characteristics and the revival of our past is one of the most important tasks of today. Therefore, guided by the wise saying, "A nation that doesn't know its past will have no future" requires a deeper understanding and careful study of the ethnocultural characteristics of the people.

Bilakińde bardur altın bilezik,
Barmaqlarda bardur tilladan yúzik.
Qollarında hinju qaslı bilezik.
Qulağına salıp tillá sırǵanı.
(You have a golden bracelet on your wrist.
There are rings on their fingers, rings of gold.
They wore bracelets with pearl-like eyebrows.
Gold earrings in his ear.)

A bracelet is a piece of jewellery worn on the wrist. It is made of precious metals with embroidery and eyebrows. A ring is a circular item made of gold, silver, and various metals for wearing on a finger. [1.347-225]. An earring is a device made of various metals for wearing on the ear [2.248].

A breastplate is a decoration worn by women on their chests, shaped like a hemisphere, with a carved pattern and a chain attached to the bottom. This word is often used in the poet's works:

Kóylegi darayı, óńir monshaqlı.
Mawıt-shekpen jáne neshe zatlarıń
(Her dress was multicolored, with pearls on her chest.
Fabric, robe, and how many more things do you have?)

The word "darayı" in the given example refers to a wide, thin fabric woven from striped silk and clothing made from it.

Mádeli túrmeli, yipek rumallı,
Atlas qamqasına aqlım hayrandur.
Bılǵarıdan kiysen mási-keyalimni.
Kiyseń árebiden qara shógirme.
Nazálimler taǵıp tillá jıǵasın.
Gewishleri tillá mıyıq qaǵılǵan.
Shashbawları bardur yipekten shashaq,
Gúlli kewish, kiygenleri zer lipas.
Kókshayı kemzalıń túshmúsh ózińe.
Qazba maqpal taqiya kiyseń basıńa.
(In a silk scarf
My mind is amazed by the atlas pattern.
If you put it on from leather, it will be my wish.
If you put on a black skullcap made of arabi.
Let the ungrateful wear gold.
Their shoes were decorated with gold earrings.
They have strands of silk.
In flowered robes, in golden robes.
The Kokchay kamzol is tied to you.
Put a carved velvet skullcap on your head.)

In the examples above, the words "mádeli turma" "yipak rumol" "kóylek" "shekpen" "mási-gewish" "shógirme" "kemzol" and "taqiya" refer to clothing, while the words "bileguzik" "júzik" "monshaq" "sirǵa" "haykel" and "shashbaw" refer to jewelry. The word "árebi" has a semantic connection with the words "Arabiya," and the word "bılǵarı" with the words "Bulgaria," denoting the origin of the material from which the product was made. The former state of Bulgaria was located on the territory of the present-day Republics of Tatarstan and Bashkortostan. The leather processing industry is highly developed in Bulgaria.

Therefore, there was strong demand for leather made in this country on the world market.

In general, studying and linguistically analyzing the terms of national clothing and jewelry in Qazi Maulik's works is of great practical and theoretical importance for a deep understanding of the vocabulary of the Karakalpak language, obtaining information about the history and ethnography of our people, and teaching them to future generations. Through the ethnographisms used in his verses, the master of artistic expression was able to depict, mainly, the life and conditions of the Karakalpak people of that time.

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